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Title: SOP for Brother PT-950NW label printer and P-touch Editor software versions 5.3 and 5.4

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Summary

This SOP will focus on the installation of the software and drivers for working with PT-950NW label maker and subsequent operating of the machine and software itself. This SOP also includes connecting in-house library database in print setup for easier printing of batches. At the end of this SOP, there is explanation of differences between specific printing options that are possible on this printer.

Brother PT-950NW – How to operate

1. Prior to start, turn on Brother PT-950NW label printer on back side (rocker switch, it is usually on; for hard turn off) and front side (classical button) to make the light in the frontal part green (Figure 1).
1. If you plan to print wireless, make sure the Wi-Fi connection button is also on and the light is green (Figure 1)
2. Check the cartridge – if you have desired size and enough of the tape.

NOTE: The Printer would show you the empty cartridge by the highest light being red (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Operating with the printer Brother PT-950NW

Installation of P-Touch Editor and needed drivers

1. Go to:
<https://support.brother.com/g/b/productsearch.aspx?c=ca&lang=en&content=dl>
2. In the box 'search by model name', paste PT-9800PCN
3. Choose operating system (probably Windows 10, 64-bit)
4. On next window select P-touch Editor 5.x
5. Agree to EULA license
6. Enter serial number **D3Z957522**

For the proper working and installation, the **driver** also needs to be downloaded and installed:

1. Go to: <https://support.brother.com/g/b/productsearch.aspx?c=ca&lang=en&content=dl>
2. In the box 'search by model name', paste PT-950NW
3. Choose operating system (probably Windows 10, 64-bit)
4. On next window select PT-950NW Driver (Figure 2)

Drivers

Title	Description	Release Date (Version)	Size
Printer Driver	This is the software required to print from a machine. For instructions to uninstall the ...more	02/15/2023 (1.10.4g)	32.49 MB
Printer Driver Uninstaller	Use Printer Driver Uninstaller if you cannot complete the printer driver installation, or if ...more	02/15/2023 (3.2.0.0)	1.24 MB

Figure 2 - Driver for the printer P950NW

5. For correct connection with your computer, choose Wireless connection (Figure 3)

Figure 3 - Wireless connection to computer

6. Open the setting of Wi-Fi on your computer and choose the Wi-Fi of the printer and connect to it (Figure 4). The password to this Wi-Fi is 00000000 (8x zero).

Figure 4 - Wi-Fi connection to the printer

7. Choose the type of the Brother machine you are installing – just click on it and click Next (Figure 5).

8. Then the printer will now be connected through the Wi-Fi to your computer.

Figure 5 - Choosing the right Printer

9. Open the P-Touch Editor software and change the Printer on the upper righthand side of the screen to PT-P950NW – it should be already saved there (Figure 6).

Figure 6 - Changing of the printer type in P-Touch

NOTE: If the Printer on the Figure 6 does not align with the type of printer you have, just click on this button and choose from the options the correct version.

Brother PT-950NW: P-touch Editor 5.3 used for label printing

1. On your computer, double-click the *P-touch Editor 5.3* icon to open software.
2. Select the New Layout or Predefined layout to be used (e.g., Asset Management → Equipment Label) and open it by double-click.
3. The label layout will appear, and you can adjust it to your needs

Connecting it with the in-house Database

1. The connection with the Database is just at the beginning of the label creating:

- In case of opening some of the **Predefined Layout** (e.g. the Equipment Label) that has database included, the window “Open Database” will open itself (Figure 7)

Figure 7 - Connection of the database to the predefined layout

- In case of opening the **New Layout**, the “Open Database” window won’t open itself and it can be opened either by the tool on the tab (Figure 8) or through File → Database → Connect (Figure 9):

Figure 8 - Open Database window - connecting with the database

Figure 9 - Opening the Open Database Window through File

2. In Open Database window (Figure 8), Connect Database File by using Browse button to connect Excel file.
3. Un-click the box “Header Row Contains Field Names” and then click Next
4. Select Database Table from your computer and then open appropriate Excel Worksheet.
5. In Open Database window, Preview (**Error! Reference source not found.**) it shows selected label, Merge Fields: shows the Database Fields to be merged with excel columns (e.g., F2, F3, F4, F5, F6).
6. Assign the corresponding excel column via Database Field to the label preview and the click **OK**.

Figure 10 - Assignment of the columns of database to the label

7. Click icon **Check media** icon to check which size of the tape is in the printer right now. There is also the possibility to adjust the label width and make some changes in structure and settings of label (width, length, size of individual windows, etc.) dependent on the figured-out size in the printer itself. This tool looks very different between the P-Touch Editor versions – Figure 11, Figure 12

Figure 12 - Check Media in P-Touch Editor 5.3

Figure 11 - Check Media in P-Touch Editor 5.4

8. Click icon “Display Dialog Box for Detailed Printer Settings” (version 5.3) or just “Print” (version 5.4) to set printing of final label. The Print window will appear, here you can set your optimal settings (Figure 13):
 - More specific options of the setup for cutting and printing are in the “Properties”

NOTE: Explanations of different setups:

- Auto Cut: the labels will be fully cut, and they will be falling out of the printer by one piece

- Half Cut: the labels are pre-cut, the underlying paper is intact, and the print will be in one piece, easy to unstick the labels down from the paper
- Chain Printing: one-piece of underlying paper will come out of the printer
- Special tape: for special needs, see in the settings itself
- Mirror printing: if the prints need to be printed upside down to print from the inner part of the piece

Figure 13 - Printing settings

9. → “Print” icon to print labels. Following printer settings like Half Cut, Chain Printing and Copies Number: e.g., 10, then ten label copies, each pre-cut for easy peeling off in one chain will be printed.